

A STUDY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AND MOTIVATION OF THE NURSES

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic crisis has shown that the job performance of physicians and nurses is crucially important for effective, efficient and uninterrupted fulfillment of health services. It is seen that the studies within the scope of performance evaluation are generally made for physicians and there is not enough research on the performance evaluation of nurses in particular. In this study, it was aimed to examine the effect of the performance evaluation system on the motivation of the nurses. Findings of the study highlight that self-performance assessment of the nurses significantly affect both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation dimensions.

Keywords: *Performance Appraisal, Motivation, Nurse, Health Sector.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic crisis has shown that the job performance of physicians and nurses is crucially important for effective, efficient and uninterrupted fulfillment of health services. It is seen that the studies within the scope of performance evaluation are generally made for physicians and there is not enough research on the performance evaluation of nurses in particular. The fact that nurse performance evaluations are made with personal evaluations rather than professional methods in the provision of health services adversely affect dynamic workforce planning and reduce the motivation of employees by preventing the execution of the performance-related reward and punishment system.

The implementation of the performance appraisal system should be based on the use of effective management and the determination of what is expected from the personnel. Planning for the improvement and development of the performance of the institution and its personnel is the most important stage of the performance appraisal process. In the planning of the performance evaluation process, it is very difficult to answer questions such as who will be best served, in what way, and how we can best show the produced service (Kabadayı, 2002).

Performance evaluation is the evaluation of the working performance of nurses according to the determined performance standards. Design of the activities of employees affect the efficiency of an organization. Therefore, performance evaluation requires good planning. It also requires collecting information about employees and then meeting them formally. In this direction, it requires the performance criteria to be clearly revealed and defined, and the activities related to the work to be measured by observation (Camgöz, 2006).

Performance evaluation would provide meaningful information within the scope of the employer, the work carried out and the employees carrying out the work. Performance evaluation, in which the expectations of the employees and the needs of the job are revealed, will lead to a meaningful communication between the employer and the employees.

In this study, it was aimed to examine the effect of the performance evaluation system on the motivation of the nurses. In the following sections, firstly the concepts of performance and motivation have been discussed. Then, the findings of the empirical study have been provided and the discussed.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Performance is a phenomenon that means the degree of success in any job and reveals what an employee does or does not. It is expressed as the fact that a public organization is more effective and efficient than others or according to its own history, shows where a person, group, work unit or institution can reach the target through that job (Usta, 2010).

In today's organizations, the productivity of the employees is crucially important. Establishment of technical possibilities where efficiency can be measured, and efficiency can be compared enables important strategies to be developed in terms of measurable success of the organization and performance.

Performance, which can be expressed as the level of fulfillment of a job or the behavior of the employee according to the determined conditions, is an indicator of what a person does or does not accomplish (Bingöl, 2010). The phenomenon of performance emerges as a result of the comparison of an individual's qualifications and abilities with business success measures arranged in relation to his job.

The performance criteria of each business or organization may differ. The process of improving these criteria is called the performance management process. Observing this process and determining the methods that should be applied between what is and what should be is to ensure the implementation of the determined methods. In this process, some of the objectives should be listed as increasing the performance in the personal and institutional sense, ensuring employee motivation, providing an objective attitude to the employees, revealing the phenomenon of organizational justice, determining the criteria for rewarding and promotion opportunities, and defining healthy business processes.

Although the health sector is a labor-intensive sector, it is an area where technological infrastructure is more prominent. Although there have been great technological advances in the field of health, the value of health workers constantly preserves its value.

Nonetheless, employees in the sector, as in other sectors, know that they will encounter appreciation and reward in cases where their professional knowledge and personal dedication are demonstrated. The productivity of health workers should be evaluated as an indicator of the efficiency of the delivery of health services. In this context, the increase in the performance of health workers will also increase the efficiency of the healthcare institutions.

When different sectors are observed, it is seen that the importance of employee performance in the health sector is higher. Because in addition to the high level of communication between the patient and the employee and those who will benefit from health services expects to receive quality and effective health services while possible mistakes in healthcare operations could lead to irreparable results.

It is also commonly noted in the literature that the management organizations that are designed correctly and in place will positively affect the said health institutions in terms of efficiency and performance. Thus, it is necessary to plan the organization and structural framework of health services within the scope of ensuring the continuity of its economic life together with its efficiency so that healthcare professionals should be satisfied with their work environment and workplaces.

Today's management approaches can deal with the concept of performance from different dimensions. Adhering to the fact that the main factor is efficiency, there is a need to analyze situations such as foresight sensitivity in the health sector, quality approaches, what is done and how it should be done, whether to provide added value in terms of the goals of the health institution. These needs reveal the necessity of measuring old and new concepts (Korkmaz, 2011). The concepts that need to be measured focus on seven different dimensions, which are efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, quality, innovation, quality of working life and profitability.

The delivery of nursing services is considered as one of the main elements of the delivery of health services today. Nursing services can be described as organizations where healthcare providers plan,

organize, perform, supervise and coordinate nursing services, follow sectoral changes and developments within the framework of institutional goals and policies and fulfill their requirements.

Nursing practices consist of knowledge of biological, psychological, behavioral and social sciences. Nursing can be defined as the diagnosis and treatment of individuals' current and potential health problems. These practices include providing care, protecting health, preventing and rehabilitating diseases and injuries (Karalili, 2011).

According to the International Council of Nurses (ICN, 2002), "Nursing encompasses autonomous and collaborative care of individuals of all ages, families, groups and communities, sick or well and in all settings. It also includes the promotion of health, prevention of illness, and the care of ill, disabled and dying people."

Nursing professionals who communicate with patients and their relatives during the preventive, diagnosis-treatment and recovery stages and provide one-to-one healthcare services provide services at similar standards all over the world. Hence, nurse performance is one of the most important productivity indicators for the health sector. Since nurse performance is evaluated in direct proportion to the number of patients per nurse per day, it also affects the service quality in the sector. Although many nursing service executives assess the input-output ratio while interpreting the productivity of nurses (Korkmaz, 2011), it is important to evaluate the work performance of nurses according to the determined performance criteria, which needs to be clearly revealed and defined (Camgöz, 2006).

As a result of the digitalization of the health sector, all kinds of information to monitor the performance of the employees can be recorded in real time. These data, which are also obtained in the field of nursing services, are accepted as a factor that facilitates evaluation in terms of performance evaluation. These digital data, which are evaluated systematically, contribute to the development of nursing services as well as performance evaluation.

Performance appraisal describes the nurse's performance and its relationship with organizational goals. It is the way to make a regular and formal evaluation of how well and how well nurses perform their duties in a certain period of time (Seyirci, 2009).

Motivation, which is one of the important factors affecting the performance of employees, has always been an important research topic in terms of academic studies. The term can generally be defined as an influencing reason to take action. Arık (1996) defines motivation as internal and external reasons and their functioning mechanisms that push people to act, determine the violence and energy level of their behaviors, give a certain direction to behaviors and ensure their continuity. In terms of Koçel (2001) definition, it is the behavior of individuals with their own desires and desires to achieve a certain goal. Palmer & Winters (1990) states that motivation is an internal force and can only be directed by the individual himself.

The desire to satisfy some logical, emotional, conscious or subconscious motivational forces is decisive in people's behavior. These motivational forces are called "needs" (Çermik, 2001). Although the needs (needs) vary from person to person, in general, they can be collected in two groups as basic and complementary needs.

Basic needs are physiological needs such as food, drink, shelter, rest and sleep that people need to maintain their lives. Some of the aforementioned needs may change and be oriented within the framework of traditions, customs and lifestyles along with regional geographical differences.

Complementary needs are less specific when considering basic needs. These needs are shaped within the framework of sociological and psychological arguments and are evaluated within the scope of human relations.

In both social life and business life, individuals seek to use time in the most efficient way by acting together. During this search, they act in accordance with social and cultural norms. This state of adaptation creates behavioral habits in human life. State and attitudes appreciated in society play a role

of need in terms of behavior patterns of individuals. When these needs are examined, it is seen that they are needs with social content.

In addition to social needs, there are also psychological needs that shape or direct the attitudes of individuals. These needs are based on thought and may occur due to psychological deficiencies. Such needs are quite complex. This complexity varies according to individuals and their personality traits. Another feature of sociological and psychological needs is gaining experience in the life process and gaining through learning. Some of these needs can be shown as personal appreciation, sense of duty responsibility, success, power, gain, compassion.

Instincts are one of the common traits that humans share with animals. It is seen that instincts are not acquired through education and training and are not forgotten throughout life. In general, instincts appear as a complex and periodic sequence of movements that come from nature and are related to lineage (Öztabağ, 1972). Although instincts are characterized as unconscious behaviors, they reflect a universal order and reaction. Behaviors such as thirst, breathing and hunger can be given as examples of instincts that do not require mastery, with different types of compensation.

Physiological motives, also known as impulses, are motives for the satisfaction of primary and basic needs in order to maintain life. It is also an important point that the continuity of the human race cannot be ensured if the physiological motives in question are not eliminated. In addition, although the physiological motives are in every individual, the severity of the motives differs between individuals (Penfield, 1969).

Unlike animals, humans can establish conscious relationships and organize life collectively thanks to social motives. Although it has been observed that animals wander in groups, no connection between their instinctive approach and consciousness has been detected. Unlike this, it is consciousness that brings people closer to each other and drags them to the phenomenon of collective life. The motivational push of people to collective life causes them to cooperate and to seek ways to use time economically.

In this process, they act in harmony with the rules, norms and traditions. The rules that ensure the continuity of collective living regulate the behavior of individuals in their lives. Behaviors appreciated by the environment play the role of a social motive within the framework of the individual's behavioral goals. These social behaviors provide the order of life and affect the formation of physiological motives (Penfield, 1969).

Apart from social motives, there are also psychological motives that create or direct the behavior styles of individuals. Such motives are revealed by spiritual and intellectual needs. These motives determine personality and behavioral characteristics. Although psychological motives are complex, they vary from person to person. Psychological motivation is sometimes the desire to be noticed and sometimes the desire to be independent, but the bond that unites them is the desire for power (Munn, 1968).

The scale developed in the studies of Mottaz (1985), Brislin et al. (2005), and Mahaney & Lederer (2006) to measure the effect of motivation factors on the performance of employees has two sub-dimensions as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. According to the intrinsic motivation perspective, employees are motivated by the work itself. There is no external control that regulates one's behavior here. Such a state of motivation can be characterized as the experience of revealing one's own abilities (Brief and Aldag, 1976).

Intrinsic motivation tools are directly related to the nature of the work and are derived from the content of the work. An interesting and challenging job includes factors such as independence at work, importance of the job for the employee, participation in the job, responsibility, diversity, creativity, opportunities to use one's talents and skills, and satisfactory feedback on one's performance (Mottaz, 1985).

Focusing on the job itself, the work of Hackman and Lawler (1971), and Hackman and Oldman (1975), identified five job characteristics that were conceptually independent and suggested that they could be applied to any job. These characteristics are;

variety of skills, identity of the job, importance of the job, independence and feedback.

According to Mottaz (1985), extrinsic motivation tools include two dimensions. While the first dimension is related to social motivation tools, the second dimension is related to organizational tools. The social motivation dimension includes factors such as friendship, helpfulness, support from colleagues and supervisors and is based on the quality of interpersonal relationships.

The organizational dimension of extrinsic motivation tools is related to the opportunities offered by the organization to increase job performance. These tools are tangible and include factors such as adequacy of resources in the workplace, equal pay, opportunity for promotion, additional benefits and job security. These factors are also called instrumental motivational tools.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between the motivation and performance levels of nurses working in in the medical faculty of a state university in Turkey. In addition, it was also aimed to understand the factors affecting the motivation and performance levels of nurses.

The working life of nurses includes quite a variety of activities and duties. The performance of nurses positively related to their interaction with patients, colleagues, executives, and other people working in the same environment. Therefore, in addition to the internal and external motivators of nurses, professional motivation, job satisfaction and organizational commitment levels are of great importance in terms of their performance.

The population of the study consists of 700 nurses working in the medical faculty of a state university in Turkey. In the study, the sample size was calculated as 149 at an acceptable error level of 5%. Face-to-face survey method has been conducted to collect the data.

The questionnaire form used in the research consists of three parts. In the first part of the questionnaire

aims to understand the demographic characteristics of the participants. In the second part, scales developed by Mottaz (1985), Brislin et al., (2005), and Mahaney and Lederer (2006) were used to measure the motivation levels of the nurses.

Finally, in the third part of the questionnaire, the scale developed by Selçuk (1998) was used to measure the effectiveness of nurses' performance evaluations. This scale measures the efficiency level of nurses in evaluating their individual job performances and the job performances of their executives. A high score in the scale, which consists of two sub-dimensions, means that the individual performance of the nurse is high and that the executives evaluate the employee performances effectively.

On the analysis of data; descriptive statistics are presented with frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation values. Exploratory factor analysis was used to determine the factor structure of the question groups in the study. Cronbach Alpha analysis was used to test the internal consistency of the dimensions. Correlation and regression analysis was applied to determine the relationships between the dimensions.

4. FINDINGS

It was determined that 148 of the participants of the study were nurses, while only one of them was midwife. The average age of the participants was 35 while their average professional experience was 12 years, and the average working time in the hospital where the research was carried out was 10 years.

Regarding the perceptions about performance appraisal of the participants in nursing; while evaluating the professional success of nurses with 13%, the way or process of providing care by nurses to patients and other people by 28%, the evaluation of nurses' efficiency and effectiveness in job presentation steps with improved scales with 41%, the evaluation of the monetary value of the labor process of nurses with 7%, 12% of the participants stated that there are subjects other than these subjects (Table 1).

Table 1. Participants' Demographic Characteristics and Opinions on Performance Appraisal

Task	n	%
Midwife	1	.7
Nurse	148	99.3
Total	149	100.0
What does performance appraisal mean in nursing?		
Evaluation of the professional success of nurses	19	12.8
Evaluation of the way or process of providing care to patients and other people by nurses	41	27.5
Evaluation of nurses' efficiency and effectiveness	61	40.9
Evaluation of the monetary value of the labor process of nurses	10	6.7
Other	18	12.1
Total	149	100.0
Is performance measurement necessary in nursing?		
Yes	137	91.9
No	12	8.1
Total	149	100.0
Does performance appraisal of nurses has an effect on work efficiency and service quality?		
Yes	139	93.3
No	10	6.7
Total	149	100.0

As can be seen in Table 2, 92% of the nurses stated that performance measurement is necessary in nursing and 93% of them stated that performance evaluation has a positive effect on work efficiency and service quality. 80% of the nurses think that performance evaluations should be explained. While

56% of the nurses stated that rewards or punishments should be made according to the results of the performance evaluations, 11% of the nurses had knowledge about at least one performance evaluation system.

Table 2. Participants View on Performance Appraisal

Should the Results of Performance Appraisal be Announced?	n	%
Yes	119	79.9
No	30	20.1
Total	149	100.0
Should Reward/Punishment Methods be Applied After Performance Appraisal?		
Yes	83	55.7
No	66	44.3
Total	149	100.0

Do You Know of Any Performance Appraisal Systems in Nursing?	n	%
Yes	16	10.7
No	133	89.3
Total	149	100.0

Who Would You Like to do the Performance Appraisal in Nursing?	n	%
My Colleagues	12	8.1
Chief Nurse	50	33.6
Service Physician	3	2.0
Floor Nurses	1	.7
Both Executives and Assistants	28	18.8
Myself	6	4.0
All	49	32.9
Total	149	100.0

As can be seen from Table 2, it is desired by the majority of nurses that performance evaluations should be carried out by the chief nurse or a mixed system.

In the survey study, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the reliability of the scale, which consists of 25 statements about measuring the motivation levels of

nurses, was determined as 0.92. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the reliability of the scale, which consists of 17 statements about measuring nurses' performance efficiency levels, was determined as 0.90. The coefficient obtained shows that the scale is reliable enough to be considered sufficient. After the reliability analysis, factor analysis was applied to the scales in order to test the construct validity.

Table 3. Reliability and Validity

Dimensions	Statements	Internal Consistency	Variance Explained (%)	Eigen Value
Intrinsic Motivation	1 - 9	0.88	34	6.65
Extrinsic Motivation	10 - 25	0.83	30	4.29
Nurses' Self Performance Assessment	1 - 10	0.80	16	4.01
Performance Assessment by Chief Nurses	11 - 17	0.76	12	3.66

As a result of the Factor Analysis, two sub-dimensions were determined in the motivation scale. These dimensions are defined as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The KMO coefficient was found as 0.89. The coefficient indicates that the sample size is sufficient for the further analyses. In addition, the dimensions obtained according to the result of the Bartlett Sphericity test, in which the significance of the factor structures were tested ($p = 0.001$, $p < 0.05$), were found significant.

Two sub-dimensions were determined in the performance effectiveness scale. These dimensions are defined as nurses' self-performance assessment and performance assessment by chief nurses. The KMO coefficient was found as 0.84. The coefficient indicates that the sample size is sufficient for the further analyses. The dimensions obtained according to the result of the Bartlett Sphericity test, in which the significance of the factor structures was tested ($p =$

0.001, $p < 0.05$), were also found significant. Finally, it was observed that the distributions of the all sub-

dimensions conformed to the normality ($n = 149$, K-S $p = 0.200^*$, $p > 0.05$)

Table 4. Modeling the Relationships Between Motivation and Performance Appraisal

Dependent Variable (Y)	R ²	Model	Nurses' Self-Performance Assessment	Performance Assessment by Chief Nurses
			β	
Intrinsic Motivation	0.13	F=17.41 p=0.001	0.322 p=0.01	No Relationship
Extrinsic Motivation	0.15	F=12.52 p=0.001	0.386 p=0.01	No Relationship

As seen in Table 4, it has been determined that the only dimension affecting intrinsic motivation is Nurses' Self-Performance Assessment. This partial relationship seems to be mathematically significant ($F = 17.41$, $p = 0.001$, $p < 0.05$). The percentage of the independent variable, explaining the changes in the intrinsic motivation dimension was found to be 13% ($R^2 = 0.13$).

Similarly, it is seen that only Nurses' Self-Performance Assessment dimension can affect the extrinsic motivation dimension. This partial relationship also seems to be mathematically significant ($F = 12.52$, $p = 0.001$, $p < 0.05$). The percentage of this dimension explaining the changes in the independent variable was found to be 15% ($R^2 = 0.15$).

5. CONCLUSION

Nurses are healthcare professionals that play a key role in ensuring communication between healthcare staff and visitors to whom the patient and their family members contact around the clock. The efficiency and effectiveness of nurses while performing their services varies depending on their motivation. For this reason, the motivation levels of nurses should be observed, and attempts should be made to increase their motivation levels and keep their performance higher.

This study was carried out to determine the relationship between the motivation levels and performance levels of nurses working in a state university hospital in Turkey. The internal consistency values of the performance and motivation sub-dimensions used in the study were calculated and it was seen that the answers given by the participants to the questionnaire were consistent.

Nurses who think that rewarding or punishing methods should be applied as a result of the performance appraisal were found to have a higher level of intrinsic motivation as a result of the performance evaluation. The reason why nurses think that rewarding or punishing methods should be applied as a result of performance appraisal is effective on intrinsic motivation is that reward or punishment is related to intrinsic motivation. Mottaz (1985) stated that rewarding and punishing employees are related to their intrinsic motivation levels. Consistent with the findings of this study, Mottaz (1985) expects that employees' rewards and punishments do not affect their extrinsic motivation levels.

The findings obtained in the study are also consistent with the findings of Karabulut and Çetinkaya (2011). Öztürk (2006) also found that the motivation levels of

nurses are indifferent according to their education levels.

In Karabulut and Çetinkaya's (2011) study, it was determined that demographic characteristics of nurses only age and working time did not have a significant effect on performance dimensions, which supports the findings of this research. In the study of Seyirci (2009), it has been observed that nurses in administrative duties have higher job performance than other nurses. These results, however, differ from the findings of this study.

In the study of Ertan (2008), it is stated that as the age of the employees increases, their intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and general work motivation increase, which is not consistent with the findings of this study. Nonetheless, the findings of Ertan (2008) also highlight that as the work experience of the employees increases, their intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation increase, relatively, that supports the findings of this study.

Similarly, Öztürk's (2006) study also reveals that the performance levels of nurses increase as the internal motivation increases. In the study of Ölçer (2005), it was stated that there is a positively significant relationship between the level of motivation and the level of performance. Köroğlu (2011) found a positive and significant relationship between job motivation and job performance in a study on the relationship between job satisfaction and the factors affecting motivation levels with performance. All these results support the findings of the study.

Various suggestions have been developed within the scope of the results obtained. First of all, studies should be carried out on the use of motivators that increase their performance by considering the motivation levels of nurses. In order to appraise the performance of nurses, the performance criteria in the organization should be determined clearly, measurably and in accordance with the truth, and should be communicated to the employees.

Furthermore, training programs can be arranged by identifying the issues with insufficient professional knowledge. A performance appraisal system suitable

for measuring the performance level of nurses should be established and the performance of employees should be measured at least once a year and promotions should be made according to these results. At the same time, making the promotions based on the seniority of the employees and having received the appropriate training for the position they will be brought to may increase the motivation and performance level of the nurses.

In order to increase the motivation of the employees, executives can consider rotations by evaluating the wishes of the employees at certain intervals. In this study, only the performance evaluation scale, in which executives and nurses themselves making the assessment, was used. In future studies, the scope of the study can be expanded by making performance measurements in which higher rank of executives and patients evaluate employees.

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